

ON THE DISEASES

WHICH

PREVAILED AMONG THE BRITISH TROOPS AT RANGOON.

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ON my return from the Burman empire, where I had been present with the army during the whole of the late war, I intended, so far as my experience and information would enable me, to have laid before the Society a general account of the diseases which prevailed amongst the British troops in the first and second campaigns ; but having found the materials would exceed the limits of an essay designed for the reading and discussion of an evening, I shall confine myself, in the following pages, (after premising a few remarks on the medical topography of the town and its vicinity,) to the consideration of the health of the troops during the first twelve or fourteen months after their occupation of Rangoon, and to the more particular description of the diseases which occurred in the hospitals of a detachment of European and native artillery under my immediate charge.

The geographical position of Rangoon is laid down in Lat. $16^{\circ} 47'$ N. Long. $96^{\circ} 9'$ E. The town, or fort, stands on the north bank of a river of the same name, about 28 miles above where it falls into the Gulf of Martaban. In length it extends along the river upwards of a mile: its breadth is 600 or 700 yards; and it is encompassed with teak-wood timbers and planks 10 or 12 feet high, having one gateway on the southern, eastern, and western face, and two on the northern front. The north side of the stockade is strengthened with a broad, but now shallow fosse, over which there is an earthen mound and a wooden bridge. From each northern gateway a good brick road leads along a gentle, but irregular rising ground; and these gradually converging together, terminate at different points, at the terrace of the Shoe-dagon pagoda, $2\frac{1}{2}$ miles to the north of the town. The space intervening between these roads being pretty clear of wood and jungle, was selected for the quartering of the troops. The houses and pagodas upon the eastern road were allotted for the accommodation of the Bengal troops, and those on the western road were consigned to the Madras division of the army, while the artillery parks of both presidencies were formed on an open plain in the centre. The ground sloped considerably towards the western side of this triangle, and the Madras lines leaned on a thick wood, which extended to, and closed in upon the north and north-east of the Great Pagoda; but on the eastern side, particu-

larly as it approaches the Dagon Pagoda, the land springs with almost precipitous abruptness from the adjacent level; and when at an elevation of nearly 200 feet above the surface of the river, the view stretches, in a S. E. direction, to a great distance over low rice ground, in which the windings of the Rangoon and Syriam rivers can be seen for several miles. During the whole of the war, this part of the country was left uncultivated; and in the rainy seasons, constituted an extensive morass, covered with rank grass and broad-leaved water plants. Within the parallelogram formed by the stockade, the houses are disposed in regular order, and the streets, for the most part, cross each other at right angles. The streets, in general of small width, are formed of pounded bricks, with a rise in the middle, so as to throw off the rain into watercourses on either side. On the arrival of the expedition, and during the first rainy season, they were much out of condition, and extremely dirty; but were subsequently put into good repair by the military Commandant of the town. The better sort of houses are substantially built of wood, supported by colonnades of teak pillars, and roofed with shingles or tiles, from 6 to 10 feet high. The houses of the lower classes are raised on bamboos about two feet from the ground; the walls are of mats, manufactured from the same useful reed; the roof is covered in with a thatch of palmetto leaves, and the flooring is formed of boards, or split cane. Besides the Custom House, there are a few other *brick* buildings in the town,

erected by foreigners. At the west end of the fort, and running in a direction parallel to the river, is the long, and now populous suburb of Tackally, many of the houses of which rise on piles from the steep and muddy bank of the stream. On the eastern extremity, and along the whole southern front of the stockade, are numerous houses, most of them supported on piles within high water mark, and communicating with each other by elevated wooden platforms, or by means of planks and boles of trees laid end to end upon the slimy beach. Towards the conclusion of the year 1824, when the inhabitants, who had fled into the interior of the country on the capture of the place, returned to their homes, this part of the town became densely peopled : and what from the peculiar odor of the exhalations from the mud of the river—the effluvia of animal and vegetable substances in process of decomposition, particularly putrid fish, which the Burmese are accustomed to use largely in the preparation of their favorite dish Balachong—their practice of depositing the refuse of their domestic economy near their doors, and of relieving nature close to, or under their houses—the air here during the ebb tide was hardly respirable by lungs unused to breathe so impure an atmosphere. The river opposite the town, from bank to bank, is 380 yards wide: its channel is deep, and its sides and bottom covered with soft mud. During the rainy season, the current runs down at the rate of 6 or 7 miles an hour, and the

tides are felt only to a short distance above the town. In the dry months, the current is much less rapid, and the tides extend their influence along the Panlang river to where it branches off from the Erawuddy, a distance of 60 or 70 miles. In the springs, the tide rises to within a couple of feet of the platform of the King's Wharf, which stands upwards of 20 feet above low water level. The water of the river is more or less turbid according to the season; but, except in the hot months, when it becomes brackish during the flood tides, it is sufficiently wholesome. Most of the varieties of fish which are common to the Hooghly and the Ganges are found here; and after the establishment of a regular bazar by the natives of the country, were always procurable in abundance, and at a reasonable rate. The water supplied to the troops was chiefly drawn from wells; and so far as my own observation goes, the quality of this was tolerably good: several medical officers were, however, of a different opinion, and set down, as a cause of the fatal dysentery which affected the army, the use of the water derived from the spring. Along the Bengal lines to the eastward are several tanks, of which one is a lake in size, and of much picturesque beauty. From the number of kilns which studded the country in their neighbourhood, it would appear that those reservoirs have been originally dug for the sake of the material for brick-making they afforded, to supply the large demand for bricks in the erection of their sacred

buildings. The smaller ones dry up during the hot season, but the lake contains water the whole year, and is well stocked with fish. Though soft and well tasted, this water was only used for watering cattle and washing clothes. It might be expected that I should say something here regarding the mineral spring near the north side of the Dagon Pagoda; but having observed, in a circular letter of the Society, that one of its members had sent a portion of it to Calcutta for chemical analysis, I concluded that the examination had been anticipated by individuals more qualified to conduct it than myself, and that any enquiries on my part would be uncalled for. It does not appear, however, that any experiments have yet been made with a view to ascertain the constituent ingredients of this water, beyond what were instituted by Captain Cox, (vide Journal of a Residence in the Burman Empire,) to whom, and for a mineralogical description of the surrounding country, I beg leave to refer. In March and April, when the water is in its most concentrated state, its sensible properties are these—colourless, and without smell—taste powerfully acid, and subastringent. Clothes dipped into it are corroded and destroyed. I have made use of this water as a detergent lotion for foul ulcers, with advantage; but in this respect its virtue is inferior to that of the solutions of sulphate of copper and nitrate of silver.

Climate.—Though Ava has been celebrated, and with justice, for the salubrity of its climate, by almost all travellers who have visited the country; yet, owing to the arrival of the army at an unfavorable season, and other causes hereafter to be mentioned, our troops suffered as much from sickness as they did at Walcheren, or, under more nearly similar circumstances, at Carthagen. Here, as in Bengal and southern India, the climatic year may be divided into the cold, the hot, and rainy seasons. In the cold season, which commences with November, and terminates towards the end of February, the days are agreeably warm; the atmosphere is pure, dense, and dry, and the nights are cold and dewy, with heavy morning fogs. A moderate N. W. wind prevails throughout, and the range of the thermometer in the shade is from 60 to 86. March and April are the hottest months; yet there is perhaps in this period a greater thermometrical range than at any other. In my house, which was built of wood, with a thatch of palm leaves, and stood, unsheltered by trees, in the artillery park, the thermometer, between two and three in the afternoon, during these months, rose to 98 and 101, and at four or five in the morning fell to 75 and 72. These diurnal variations of temperature did not, however, prove injurious to health: on the contrary, the grateful coolness of the nights, by admitting of sound and refreshing sleep, made

large compensation for the oppression and languor experienced from the heat of the day. The air is excessively dry ; a light tremulous haze appears in the atmosphere, and the sky is without a cloud. The wind is generally from the N. W. ; but during the hottest hours of the day, it not unfrequently veers all round the compass, forming whirlwinds of dust, and endangering by its violence the roofs of the houses. The first showers fall early in May, and continue to fall heavy at times during the month, by which time the face of the country, from being parched and withered, is rapidly clothed with a rich and luxuriant herbage. About the end of the first week in June, the regular rains may be said to set in ; and they finally cease about the 10th or 15th of October. In 1824, the quantity of rain that fell at Rangoon was astonishingly great, compared with that which falls in ordinary seasons in Hindoostan ; and often, during the months of July and August in particular, continued with but little intermission to pour down in deluging torrents for several days and nights together. In the rainy months, the mutations of temperature are frequent and sudden. Between the showers the air is hot, close, and moist ; an atmosphere of steam seems to float around, and we breathe as if immersed in a vapour bath : all at once the sky is overcast, the rain descends heavily, accompanied with a cold, rushing wind, and the thermometer sinks 10 or 12 degrees. A damp unpleasant chill is the consequence, and people are compelled to

lay aside their light cotton for their warmer wool-
len clothes. Again the rain ceases, the sun breaks
forth, the muggy weather returns, and the cottons
are resumed. In such a country, and at such a sea-
son, it is obvious that troops engaged in active mi-
litary operations could not long withstand the en-
croachments of disease; and so, indeed, it happen-
ed. From June to October, inclusive, the princi-
pal diseases which affected the European part of
the force were dysentery and remittent fever. Dy-
sentery, remittent and intermittent fevers, prevail-
ed extensively amongst the sepoy and native
followers, and many cases of cholera occurred
amongst both. Hospital gangrene and scurvy
broke out in August and September, and shall be
noticed, at some length, under their respective
heads. The pyrexial epidemic which visited Cal-
cutta in May, and spread over a great portion of
India during the two succeeding months, also pre-
vailed at Rangoon in June and July; but as this
disease has already attracted as much attention as
its pathological importance appears to merit, I shall
here pass it over with the single remark, that it
chiefly affected the officers of the army, of whom
but few escaped, and in no instance did I hear of
its having proved fatal. In the month of August,
there was an alarming mortality amongst the men
of the Madras European regiment, from a disease
which, in its progress and termination, was said to
have borne a strong similitude to the Beriberi of
Ceylon: of this, however, I do not speak from per-

sonal knowledge, but have reason to believe that such was the fact.

During June, July, August, September, and October, the average monthly admissions into hospital from the artillery was 65 Europeans, and 62 natives; being nearly $\frac{1}{3}$ of the greatest numerical strength of the former, and $\frac{1}{4}$ of the latter; and large as was this number, I am assured that it was considerably less, in proportion, than that which was exhibited by any (at least European) regiment in either division of the army. The aggregate number of artillery in hospital, during the whole 14 months, to which this account is limited, was 605 Europeans and 687 natives, a large proportion being made up of readmissions for dysentery. Of the former 49 died, (including 12 who died in the field hospitals of Rangoon and Mergui,) or a fraction less than 1 in $12\frac{1}{2}$. Amongst the latter 34 deaths occurred, or somewhat less than 1 in 20. On the setting in of the cold season, the general sickness began to decline, and from January to July 1825, was comparatively moderate*.

I shall now proceed to give as compendious a description as I can, consistent with perspicuity, of the principal diseases, their symptoms, causes,

* The change of season brought no relief to those who were affected with chronic or scorbutic dysentery, and but few of those patients who remained in the country attained robust health.

and treatment, which occurred in the European and native hospital of the detachment of artillery.

DYSENTERY.

This disease began to manifest itself amongst the European troops at a very early period after their arrival. Rangoon was taken by storm on the 11th May 1824, and till July 1825 more than half the number of admissions into my hospital were for this complaint alone, being in the proportion of 516 to 972. In its most acute form, the disorder was characterized by severe griping pains in the bowels, constant *desiderium dejiciendi*, and violent tenesmus: the abdomen was swelled and painful on pressure, particularly in the region of the umbilicus; the stools were generally composed of a green gelatinous matter, with admixture of muculent feces, tinged or streaked with blood; the pulse was full, strong, and frequent; the skin hot, the tongue white, and the thirst great. Nine tenths of the cases were, however, less vehement in their symptoms. After some days, or even weeks of purging, in which they had been passing, by their own account, nothing but "blood and corruption," the increasing debility and the severity of the tormina and tenesmus would compel them to appear in hospital. At this period of the disease, the stools varied much in different individuals: sometimes they were of a grass green and curdled aspect, mixed with blood; at other times they consisted of semi-liquid feces and dark fluid bile, or

were of a variegated character, green, yellow, red, and white, from the intermixture of bile, feces, blood, and puriform matter. Not unfrequently there was fixed pain in the hypogastric or umbilical regions, which was augmented on pressure; but in many cases, manipulation of the abdomen created little or no uneasiness. There was no febrile heat, thirst, or excitation of pulse: nausea and vomiting were unusual symptoms; and though the strength was impaired, the appetite often remained tolerably good, till a late period. In the progress of the disease, often in the course of the same day, the stools would vary both in color and consistency; and except in the last stage, their fetor was always less than in the healthy state. A smarting sensation of heat in the rectum was now and then complained of, as occurring at stool, and Hæmorrhoids, Prolapsus Ani and Dysuria were occasionally induced by the severity of the tenesmus. When the disease proceeded to a fatal termination, the dejections became of a bloody and watery, or green and watery appearance, and insufferably offensive smell; an inelastic puffy swelling affected the abdomen; the pulse, from being moderately full, and of its natural frequency, became quick and feeble; the appetite ceased; the thirst became insatiable; and the strength rapidly declined. In the chronic stage, or during the progress of recovery from the acute form of the disease, the alvine evacuations assumed a variety of hues, light or dark olive, bluish grey, white or

cream color; and, sometimes long after the feces had acquired a healthy consistency, an extraordinary quantity of puriform matter would be passed along with them*.

The convalescence was in most instances extremely slow. The relapses were numerous, and not a few were carried off after a third, and even a fourth attack. Another and more formidable variety of the disease occurred, which, with propriety, may be termed *Colinitis*. On the dissection of those who die of other forms of dysentery, I am aware that the great intestines are found to have suffered more or less severely; but this would seem to arise from contiguity, and the extension of the inflammation from the small intestines in which the disease *originates*, as appears from the *umbilical* and *hypogastric* regions being in the early stage the seat of pain†. Here, however, the colon and rectum are *primarily* affected; the morbid action, when it extends to the Ilium, is always in a

* The appearance of the intestinal evacuations will of course often depend on the coloring matter or chemical agency of the medicines administered. That calomel, for instance, has the effect of altering the healthy secretions of the bowels, and producing the bluish grey color of the stools noticed by Mr. Annesley, I have no doubt; but in dysentery, when the secretions undergo a morbid change, this effect by no means uniformly results from the mixture.

† That dysentery is ever, in any case, a disease of the small intestines, is an opinion which I know will be thought heterodox by many of my professional brethren; but unless it be satisfactorily shewn, that the often exquisite pain and tenderness in the central and hypogas-

less degree; and in some instances this gut does not appear to be in any way affected by the disease. The distinction between this and other forms of the disorder is one of practical utility, in as much as it differs in its symptoms, and requires a different mode of treatment. In Colitis, pain, on pressure, is generally complained of along the whole track of the intestine, from the caput cæcum to its termination in the rectum. For the most part the pain is obtuse, but at times of a more acute nature, and in such cases most sensibly felt in that part of the abdomen which corresponds with the centre and right of the arch of the colon and its sigmoid flexure. Occasionally this diagnostic symptom is entirely wanting: the roughest manipulation of the belly excites no other uneasiness than a healthy person would experience, if subjected to such an examination, and that too in patients in whom dissection has shewn that the most extensive ulceration must have been going on at the time in both the colon and rectum. In this variety of dysentery, there is not that incessant desire of going to stool that occurs in the common forms of the complaint. The purging, the tormina, and tenesmus are comparatively moderate; while, on the other hand, the general debility and

tric regions of the abdomen, present in the first stage of the disorder, are entirely dependent on consensual irritation or nervous sympathy, I hold it to be a legitimate inference, that the disease has frequently its local origin there.

mental depression are remarkably great. The stools are seldom of a bilious character, and rather indicate a deficiency or suppression of the hepatic secretions. At first they are most frequently of a light yellow and semifluid appearance, with, or without blood—latterly they become bloody, purulent, and highly fetid. With a view to its farther illustration, I shall subjoin two cases of the disease, together with an account of the morbid appearances on examination of the bodies after death.

How far the liver is implicated in the production of dysentery, is a question on which I am not competent to offer a decided opinion. That the functions of this organ are impaired, almost, from the very commencement, is a fact too well established to need confirmation; but in all the dissections I have made of those who died of the disease, no organic lesion was ever discernible in this viscus*.

Amongst the natives of the detachment, the disease was much less prevalent, and somewhat milder in its symptoms, than amongst the Europeans; but the mortality in proportion to the number of sick

* It will tend to shew the little disposition to liver complaint there was at Rangoon, when I state, that only two cases of Hepatitis came under my care, and of these, one was transferred over to me from the hospital by the Rocket Troop.

not the less great ; a fact mainly to be attributed to the want of those comforts in diet and clothing with which the latter were furnished, and from which religious prejudices and other reasons excluded the former.

CAUSES.

On the capture of Rangoon, the enemy withdrew into the woods and jungles, a few miles to the north and west of the town, and towards the great Syriam Pagoda on the east, where they constructed a line of stockades, with the view of cutting off our communications with the peaceably disposed inhabitants. To destroy these strong holds, it became necessary from time to time to send out detachments of troops, during the rains, when the country was becoming daily more and more unsuitable for military movements ; on which account the soldiers became unavoidably exposed to difficulties and hardships of the most arduous and trying nature :—at one time, forcing their passage through a dense jungle, which but for the hand of the pioneer, would have been impenetrable, and in which intense heat was untempered by a breath of air ; at another toiling over a marshy plain, up to their ankles and knees in water ; now drenched with rain, and chilled with cold ; and anon scorched by the rays of a burning sun. If to these circumstances, it be added, that the troops were unprovided with camp equipage of any description,

that their provisions were of an unwholesome kind*, and that the ordinary duties of sentry and picquet subjected them much to the influence of atmospherical vicissitudes, we shall be at no loss to account for the invasion, and rapid spread of this destructive malady.

TREATMENT.

There are few diseases, in which delay in the application of the remedies is productive of worse consequences than in dysentery ; and hence, with soldiers, who are ever known to submit reluctantly to the restraints and privations of an hospital, it often happens that the success of the treatment is nearly in an inverse ratio to the mildness of the early symptoms. The remark applies with peculiar force to the cases which occurred in this country during the first four or five months. In almost daily expectation of being called upon to oppose the enemy, and unwilling to exchange their ration-liquor, and the freedom of their lines, for the regimen and confinement of an ill-provided hospital, there were few who applied for relief, till the severity of the symptoms and constitutional derangement left them no alternative. The most tractable cases were those in which the pulse was full, strong, and frequent, with much pain and tenderness about the central part, or over the whole abdomen ; urgent tormina and tenesmus ; bilious and bloody stools. When such patients presented themselves,

* Vide Scurvy.

the practice was to take 20 or 25 oz. of blood from the arm, and to exhibit 20 grains of calomel. Four hours after, a dose of castor oil, or salts and senna was given, by the operation of which the stools became copious, and the griping and straining were diminished. The abdomen was fomented with warm water for half an hour, and a large blister subsequently laid over it, while the scruple doses of calomel were directed to be continued every four hours to the third or fourth time. After the lapse of 12 or 16 hours, it was usually found that the pulse had fallen to its natural standard, and that the tormina and tenesmus were considerably abated; in which case, the dose of calomel was reduced to five grains, and given in combination with three or four grains of antimonial powder, and half a grain of opium every four hours till the mouth became sore. When this effect was speedily induced, the patient's safety was ensured. From that hour the fixed pain in the abdomen was entirely removed, or at least was no longer complained of; the griping ceased; the stools assumed a more healthy aspect; and were passed with but little exertion; in short the patient was convalescent. This rapid introduction of mercury into the system was apt, no doubt, (and the objection has been strongly urged by some writers,) to excite painful swelling of the mouth and fauces, and severe ptyalism; but compared with the magnitude of the benefit received, and when the importance of cutting short the disease at an early period is considered, these un-

pleasant consequences were of small weight in the balance. When no febrile symptoms were present, and yet much sense of soreness in the abdomen complained of, with urgent tormina and tenesmus, the same mode of treatment was pursued, with the exception of V. S. being omitted, and the first dose of calomel accompanied with two grains of opium; an addition warranted by the less degree of inflammatory action present, and the soothing effect it produced on the bowels previous to the administration of the purgative.

Frictions with mercurial liniment on the thighs and belly were employed, when from the violence of the symptoms, and the tardy operation of the medicines, the most energetic measures became necessary; and when from idiosyncrasy or other cause, the mercury failed to affect the system, the prognosis was generally unfavorable. When the disease was of a more chronic nature, and had existed for a week or two, instead of the scruple doses of calomel, I preferred giving at first the Extr. Colocynth. C. and Pil. Hyd. of each 10 grains, and repeating it, if required, for the full evacuation of the intestines, directing the medicine noted below to be afterwards taken every four hours till the mouth was affected, or the disease gave way*.

Such was the basis of the treatment in the above

* R. Submur. Hydrarg. Pulv. Antimon. *aa* gr. iv. Ipecac. gr. ii. Opil. gr. ss. ft. pil. ii.

states of the disease. With regard to the subordinate remedies employed, they were such as were calculated to allay particular symptoms, and restore the tone and functions of the stomach and bowels. Strangury and tenesmus were relieved by sitting over the steam of hot water, and by the use of opiate enemata and suppositories. The sense of scalding heat in the rectum was diminished or removed by the carbonate of magnesia given in doses of one or two drams; and when the continuance or return of griping seemed to indicate the existence of fecal accumulations in the intestinal canal, purging clysters, and small doses of rhubarb and the neutral salts were most useful. Sudorifics, from the impossibility of preserving in patients who are frequently going to stool, that equability of temperature which is necessary to the continued and salutary flow of perspiration, did not appear to be of much utility; but warm diluents copiously drunk, and flannel worn next the skin, were important adjuvants in the cure. When the bowels remained in a loose state, which was generally the case after the cessation of the griping and tenesmus, the cure was slowly effected by the vegetable tonics and astringents; nitric acid; port wine; and such articles of nutriment as the scanty stores of the Commissariat Department admitted of supply*. With regard to the treatment of Colonitis, I regret to say, that my knowledge is almost entirely of a negative character. Mercurials, so eminently use-

* For an account of the diet of the sick, vide Scurvy.

ful in other forms of tropical dysentery, are here of no avail, either in the acute or chronic, in the first or last stage of the disease. In recent cases, when there is a considerable degree of active inflammation, much caution is required in the administration of purgatives, even a medium dose being apt to occasion excessive irritation and hyper-catharsis. Ten grains of rhubarb, and four grains of Ipecacuan, repeated if necessary, I found to be here a purgative both safe and efficient. The pain in the abdomen was seldom so great as to call for the application of a blister, and in no case have I seen any material relief obtained from its employment. In some instances, I exhibited clysters composed of two drams of the powder of Ipecacuan and a pint of warm rice gruel, to which were added two drams of laudanum; but I cannot affirm I ever saw any further good effects from them than the temporary alleviation of the tenesmus, in producing which it is probable the Ipecacuan had no share. In the advanced period of the disease, when yellow, feculent stools, mixed with blood and purulent matter, point out the existence of a low chronic ulceration of the mucous membrane of the intestines, I have prescribed a course of laxatives with some advantage. One of the compound rhubarb pills given two or three times a day, seldom failed to relieve the uneasy straining at stool, by facilitating the expulsion of the morbid secretions, and by the gently stimulating and detersive properties of the myrrh and aloes it con-

tains. In the last stage, when the stools become liquid and putrescent, and the pulse is small and feeble, opiates, wine, and nourishing diet may prolong for a few days the life of the patient.

At a subsequent period, when my experience of the disease had become more extensive, I was led to adopt, in the first or more inflammatory stage, the practice of applying leeches to the perineum, and by this means the most decided relief was almost uniformly obtained. On reference to the anatomical distribution of the veins in this part of the body, it will readily be perceived how directly the abstraction of blood from the perineum must operate in depleting the vessels of the colon; and I am confident the practice would be found of the highest utility, in all cases of dysentery where the great intestines are actively implicated in the disease.

CASE OF GUNNER RICHARD WILLIAMSON.

Was admitted into hospital on the 16th June 1825, affected for the third or fourth time with bowel complaint, and died on the 21st July following. His stools at first were of a yellowish, cream color, and semifluid consistence, occasionally streaked with blood, and accompanied with straining. By this and previous attacks, his health had suffered much—his face was pale—his body attenuated, and his appetite impaired. The rough-

est manipulation of his abdomen excited no pain ; his pulse was soft and slow ; his tongue clean ; and his stools, which had a greater or less consistency in proportion to their being less or more frequent, usually ran from three or four to seven or eight in the 24 hours.

For some time he seemed to improve under the internal use of the vegetable tonics and astringents in combination ; opiates ; small doses of rhubarb, and cathartic enemata, as circumstances made them necessary. About the 14th of July, an unfavorable change took place : griping, of which he had not before complained, now came on ; the tenesmus increased ; the stools became more frequent, and were of a dark red and watery appearance, and highly offensive odor ; pressure on the left lumbar and iliac region made him shrink from pain ; his pulse rose in frequency, and decreased in strength ; his spirits sunk, his appetite forsook him, and his strength rapidly declined. On the morning of the 21st, he complained of exquisite pain and tenderness in the pubic and left inguinal regions, which he said had come on in the course of the preceding night ; his extremities were cold, and his pulse was hardly perceptible at the wrist. In this almost hopeless state, fomentations, topical bleeding and blistering, were had recourse to without effect, and he expired about four o'clock in the afternoon.

Dissection on the following Morning.—Smell of the body exceedingly offensive;—extensive inflammation of the peritoneal coat of the intestines and abdominal parietes; effusion of coagulable lymph upon the surface of the bowels, and agglutination of their convolutions to each other;—rectum black and mortified, with rupture of its coat, and escape of its highly fetid contents into the cavity of the abdomen;—inner membrane of the colon lined with a thick bloody mucus, and abraded and ulcerated through its whole extent. In the caput cæcum were several large dark spots, from extravasation of blood; and in common with the rest of the gut, this portion of it was greatly thickened in its substance. The ilium contained a quantity of pultaceous yellow feces, and was internally sound; as was also the jejunum, duodenum, and stomach. The gibbous surface of the liver was of a paler hue than usual, but its concave side was of a bluish color. The gall-bladder was nearly full of a black, viscid bile, which, when allowed to fall in threads from the fingers, appeared, in the light, of a reddish brown color. Spleen small, but healthy. Kidneys and urinary bladder in their natural state. Thorax: Upwards of three drams of serum in the pericardium. Viscera sound.

REMARKS.

In this case there appears to have existed for several weeks a low chronic inflammation of the large intestines; which under dietetic restrictions

and medical treatment seemed to have been subsiding, when from some unknown cause it unexpectedly assumed the active form of the disease. The introduction of spirituous liquors and improper articles of food into regimental hospitals, at all times so difficult of prevention, was at this time facilitated by the removal of the native sentries to meet the exigencies of the public service; and I have little doubt but that spirits had actually been conveyed to this unfortunate patient by his well-meaning, but misjudging comrades.

GUNNER BREEN KEAN. Admitted 11th June; died 20th July, 1825.

This was a case of the chronic disease, complicated with œdema of the lower extremities and hydrothorax. The stools from first to last were either of a yellow, frothy, and semifluid aspect, or of a whitish clay color, and thin pultaceous consistency, attended for the most part with straining, and the discharge *per anum* of a few drops of venous blood. He had seldom any griping, and never complained of pain in his abdomen, even when strongly pressed by the hand. About ten or twelve days after he came into hospital, he became affected with pains in his legs, and his feet began to swell. These symptoms were succeeded by difficulty of breathing when in a horizontal position, which gradually increased till he could only rest in the semi-erect posture. The œdema at

length reached his knees, and his strength daily declined; but till within a few days of his death, his pulse was of its natural frequency, and moderately full, his appetite was good, tongue clean, thirst not great, urine of a straw color, and tolerably abundant, and except on the score of debility, and some degree of straining at stool, his feelings were generally comfortable. On the 19th, his pulse was somewhat accelerated, and his stools were more frequent and loose than before, but otherwise unaltered. In the course of the evening, the flow of his urine was occasionally interrupted by the momentary impaction of some soft solid body in the urethra. About 4 o'clock next morning, he was seized with slight convulsions, and died in a few minutes.

DISSECTION.

The morbid appearances were here almost exclusively confined to the great intestines. The canal of the colon and rectum was diminished in diameter, and its sides were condensed and thickened in their structure. Their internal surfaces exhibited an almost uniform light blush of inflammation, and the mucous membrane was perforated by innumerable small white ulcers, of a circular or oval form, with flat edges, as if so many portions of it had been snipped out. In the head of the colon there was an ulcer of the size of a sixpence, level around the circumference, but deepening towards the centre, at which point the muscular

coat was almost corroded through. The small intestines, internally and externally, had a bleached, exsanguous appearance. The liver, on its most convex part, was of a dark blue color, and the incision of it by the scalpel was followed by a stream of atrabiliary blood. The gall-bladder was nearly full of a light ochre colored bile. The vesica urinaria was somewhat thickened, and contained a small quantity of limpid urine.

Thorax.—In the right cavity of the mediastinum, there was a pint and half of a clear yellow serum, in which floated two thick cords of coagulable lymph. In the left side of the chest were found two oz. of a similar fluid ; as was also half an oz. more within the pericardium. Parietes of the heart weak and flaccid. No traces discernible of previously existing inflammation of the pulmonary or costal pleura.

REMARKS.

The early appearance of hydropic symptoms in this case, and the low asthenic state of the patient, led me to the employment of mercury in combination with squills*, with the view of rousing into activity the weakened powers of the absorbent system. On the 6th day, his mouth became sore, and a slight ptyalism taking place, its use was discontinued. Under this course his breathing was

* *R. Submur. Hyd. gr. iii. Pulv. Scillæ, gr. i. ss. Opii. gr. i. M. ft. pil. octava quaque hora sumenda.*

relieved, and there was an evident detumescence of the anasaruous limbs; but upon the bowel complaint the mercury seemed to have no effect, good or bad. Astringents, Opiates, Ipecacuan Injections, &c. availed as little, and the disease proceeded unchecked to its fatal issue. The diet of this patient consisted of lean meat soups, sago, and arrow-root, with a pint of ale, and three glasses of port wine in the day.

HOSPITAL GANGRENE.

This disease commenced in the month of August 1824, increased during the ensuing cold season, and declined on the setting in of the rains. Those whom it affected were the Sepoys, the Native followers of the army, the Chinese labourers, and a few Burman prisoners of war. The Europeans escaped it entirely.

It will be unnecessary for me to say much regarding the appearance and progress of a malady which has been so ably described by several of the most distinguished surgeons of the present day. In the numerous cases which I saw in the field hospital, in charge of Mr. Tweedie, as also in those which occurred amongst the Lascars of the Detachment of Artillery, the disease (except when wounds or ulcers on other parts took on the morbid action) uniformly began on the lower extremities, and most frequently upon the inner or outer malleolus. From thence it spread with more or less

rapidity across the dorsum of the foot, and upwards along the leg, till it destroyed, in some instances, the almost entire substance of the calf. In this state of the limb, the fetor was intolerable, a putrid bloody sanies distilled copiously from the pendulous masses of skin, muscles, tendons, and blood-vessels; constitutional derangement kept pace with the disorganization of the soft parts, and the severity of the pain; the pulse became small, quick, and often hard; and inability to sleep, loss of appetite, and colliquative solution of bowels, at length brought to a period the life and the sufferings of the patient. This is an extreme case, and happily not one of this description came under my own management. Many such, however, were treated by Mr. Tweedie, of whom but very few survived; and those, with one or two exceptions, owed their recovery to the amputation of their limbs. In by far the greater number of cases, the disease shewed itself in a much milder character. About the third or fourth day, or sometimes later, a ring of phlegmonous inflammation, succeeding to the dark œdematous circle, formed a boundary between the dead and living parts; the sloughs came away with the poultices, and detergent washes and simple dressings completed the cure.

The occasional and predisposing causes of the disorder, as they relate to the Hindoos, Mussulmans, and Burmese, may be summed up in a few words. Breathing a vitiated or tainted atmo-

sphere, consequent on the predilection of those people for living in dark, close, and airless houses—uncleanliness of person and habit—impoverished diet—liability to external injuries from the unprotected state of their limbs—lastly, scorbutic diathesis, which I have elsewhere noticed as having manifested itself almost simultaneously with these sores. The occasional causes here laid down do not appear strictly applicable to the case of the Chinese labourers. These people are naturally cleanly in their persons, and so far as my knowledge of their habits, both at Canton and other places, enables me to judge, they are well acquainted with the advantages derived from commodiously constructed and well ventilated houses*. To the predisposing causes, however, they were equally subject with the other classes: for though uninfluenced by the prejudices of caste in the choice of their food, every article of diet for many months was so scanty and expensive, as to expose them alike to similar privations.

TREATMENT.

A variety of stimulating Unguents and Lotions:—Warm Dressings, Liquor Arsenicalis, Mercurial Ointment, Tincture of Myrrh and of Aloes, Spirits of Turpentine, Lime Juice, and Alcohol, &c. were employed, but were productive of little or only

* Like other people, the Chinese were of course obliged to occupy such houses as were provided for them; but the means of converting them into comfortable tenements rested with themselves.

temporary benefit. The charcoal and fermenting poultices were very efficacious in checking the progress of the gangrene; and after the separation of the sloughs, detergent washes containing the Nitras Argenti, or Sulphas Cupri, and mild dressings, soon brought the sores to the condition of a simple and easily curable ulcer. I repeatedly tried the method recommended by M. Dussassoy, of laying a thick covering of the Pulv. Cinchonæ over the sore, and then moistening it with the Ol. Terebinthinæ; but I found the caking of this paste created so much pain, that I was obliged to relinquish its employment. Towards the end of October, when the disease was complicated with scorbutic symptoms, Lime Juice and the Nitric Vinegar were given to the extent of four, six, and eight oz. a day, but I did not perceive that any impression was made by those medicines, either upon the one disease or the other. Opiates to relieve the pain, and bark and wine when the inflammation and febrile symptoms were moderate, were the only internal remedies from which benefit was received.

Three amputations for this complaint were performed by Mr. Tweedie, when the patients* had become much exhausted by severe pain and colliquative diarrhœa. In the first of these cases, gangrene affected the stump, and the man died three days after the operation. The second lived for two months, and the wound was tardily healing,

* A coolee, a sweeper, and a rowboatman.

when it began to put on a pale and flabby appearance, an ill conditioned discharge took place, and he sunk eventually from exhaustion. In the last case, the cure proceeded as favourably as could have been desired; the diarrhœa almost immediately ceased; the pulse became more full, and sunk to its natural standard of frequency; his appetite returned; and the stump continued to heal by the first intention, and when nearly cicatrized, the man was invalided, and sent to Bengal. These cases appear to afford some encouragement to the performance of amputation in this malignant disease; and we ought not, therefore, to be deterred by the dread of the re-appearance of gangrene on the face of the stump, from removing the limb, when by the extensive destruction of the soft parts, and vehement constitutional disturbance, the patient's life is placed in imminent danger. Even when the operation fails to cure, the surgeon will at least have the gratification of rendering the last hours of the patient comparatively easy, by changing the agonizing pain of the morbid limb for the more endurable suffering of a simple incised wound.*

* In recommending amputation of the limb under the above circumstances, I am borne out by the experience of Mr. Assistant Surgeon Leslie of the 65th Regiment B. N. I. stationed at Penang. Of nine amputations performed by that gentleman for gangrenous ulcer, during the months of March and April of the present year, five of the patients are stated to have completely recovered; and there can be little doubt many more might have been saved, had the operation been oftener resorted to.

SCURVY.

This disease did not shew itself prominently amongst the European troops till towards the end of September; and it was somewhat later before it broke out amongst the Native part of the force. During the month of October, there were 16 admissions for the complaint into the European hospital of the artillery, of which the symptoms were these—swollen, loose, and livid gums, with ulcerated or sloughing edges, fetid breath, pain and hardness in the calves of the legs, contractions of the hams, and purplish discoloration of the skin, particularly of the lower extremities. To those affections were associated, in many instances, diarrhoea and œdematous swellings of the feet. Ascites in one case supervened, and universal Anasarca in another. After the month of November, there were no admissions under the head of Scorbutus; but even so late as February, a scorbutic diathesis was strongly marked in almost every case of Dysentery; and so slow was the recovery, and so inefficacious were the remedies, that I gladly availed myself of an opportunity which offered, about the middle of that month, of sending 17 of those patients to Mergui*.

* A seaport town, and the capital of a province in the southernmost part of the Burman empire, which had recently been captured by a detachment of troops under Lieut. Col. Miles. Here two field hospitals were established; and the air of the place being cool and salubrious, and vegetables and other provisions abundant, the sick derived much benefit from the change.

Amongst the Natives of our Detachment, exclusive of those who belonged to the Train and Quarter-master's establishment, (of whom no return is made in the hospital registers,) there were from first to last, that is, from October till the final disappearance of the disease in April following, 32 cases of scurvy; of these nine died, four were sent to Bengal, and 19 recovered. The same general symptoms characterized the disease in the case of the Natives as of the Europeans, with this difference, that, in the former, dysentery was less frequent, and the debility, loss of appetite, and hydroptic symptoms were more remarkable. In all the worst cases, the feet became œdematous; and however apparently mild the other symptoms might have been, this affection was an almost certain prognostic of approaching anasarca, hydrothorax, and death. One man had his gums in an enormously enlarged and fungous state; his teeth were loose, and his breath was insufferably offensive: yet this individual complained more of the painful distension of his cheeks, and inability to eat, than of any thing else; and he was one of the four who were sent to Bengal for their recovery.

CAUSES.

On the capture of the town, the system adopted by the enemy of compelling the inhabitants to withdraw into the interior of the country, and the vigilance they exerted in cutting off the supply of provisions, having thrown the army upon its

own resources for the means of subsistence, it became necessary to issue the salt meat, biscuit, and rum which the shipping afforded, in daily rations to the troops. Unfortunately the quality of the two first mentioned articles was of the worst kind. The salt beef and pork, from being badly cured and long kept, was much tainted, and often so far advanced in a state of putridity, as to be altogether unfit for use. The biscuit, coarse and mouldy from the first, became animated with insects, and after two or three months was served out to the troops, comminuted into fragments, or reduced to dust. Upon such a diet as this, unprovided with any of those grateful corrigents of salted food so long used in ships of war and merchantmen at sea, and exposed to harassing or fatiguing duties, in an inclement season, as well by night as by day, the disease in the long run was inevitable; and it is only surprising that it should have appeared at so late a period, and in so mild a form. It is in my experience to have seen this disease break out amongst the H. C. recruits, during their passage to India, in less than three months from their leaving England; and that too where the salted meat in use was of unexceptionable quality, and when a sufficiency of potatoes, mustard, and vinegar was supplied along with it*. Yet when

* The confined air of the orlop deck, allotted for the accommodation of the recruits, the transition from an active to an inactive life, and the non-observance of personal cleanliness, no doubt contributed materially

we calculate from the time of the arrival of the armament at Rangoon, and allow one month for its passage thither from Calcutta*, we shall find that the European troops actually subsisted on salt provisions for a period of $6\frac{1}{2}$ months, it not being till the 24th of October that fresh meat was regularly substituted†. Even the hospital diet rolls for the first five months exhibit only a meagre account of sago, arrowroot, wine, tea, and sugar, as nearly the whole sustenance of the sick.—On the 5th of October, and from thenceforward, the hospitals were supplied with fresh bread; and after the 19th of the same month, if we except a sufficiency of recent vegetable food, the patients were provided with every requisite. The influence of salted and putrescent animal diet in the production of scurvy is not applicable to the case of the native troops and camp followers, who suffered from the disease in equal measure with the Europeans. The daily rations furnished to those classes by the Commissariat, consisted of rice and *dal*‡, with a modicum of salt and ghee. Such articles, it may be said, form the chief food of those people in their own country, and that, though affording but little nutriment, are suited to their constitution

here to the production of the disease. The laziest, the filthiest, and the women, in particular, were first affected.

* I speak here of the Bengal troops only.

† A meal of fresh meat might have been given previous to this, and I believe was given, to the troops generally, about once a month.

‡ Split peas.

and habits : and no doubt this is the fact ; but it is at the same time well known, that they are accustomed to use greens and other pot-herbs in large quantity, and that the poorest of the Mussulman community can always command a curry of meat or of fish. At Rangoon, however, these things for a long period were beyond their reach, or attainable only in such small quantities as to operate in a very slight degree in retarding the approach of the disease. So far as I could learn, the quality of the rice, dal, &c. issued by the Commissariat was good ; and hence the great exciting cause of the scorbutic affection which existed among the native portion of the force cannot be referred to the use of a salt, putrescent, or vitiated aliment, but to defective nutrition, and the want of that vital principle contained in recent vegetable matter which is eliminated during the process of digestion and assimilation.

CURE.

The only substance possessing antiscorbutic virtues which was procurable on the first appearance of the disease, was vinegar ; and this being brought largely into requisition, and converted into the Nitrous Vinegar of Mr. Patterson, was exhibited to the extent of 6 and 8 oz. a day.—To this remedy I gave a trial of somewhat more than a month, when a supply of Lime Juice having arrived from Bengal, it was discontinued. In a few cases the nitrous vinegar excited an uneasy pun-

gent sensation in the stomach, and made it necessary to give it diluted with water; but in general it occasioned no inconvenience, even when administered in doses of 2 oz. With regard to its efficacy as a remedy in this complaint, I have to state, that it seemed to answer completely in those Europeans in whom the disease was uncomplicated with dysentery; but in no instance where the latter disorder was present, did I observe any marked benefit to result from its use.—It is but justice, however, to mention, that its failure in such cases was in common with the Lime Juice, and every other medicine employed.—In the month of September, the scorbutic patients were liberally supplied with Hodgson's ale, and spruce beer*; and in November, Pumpkins, Limes, and Oranges, were served out to them in small quantities, which, though insufficient for the cure, appeared to have the effect of checking the disease, or rendering it stationary. The bowel complaint was wholly of a chronic nature; the purging was seldom of excessive frequency; the stools were usually of a semifluid consistence, and of a green, yellow, or cream color: some degree of tenesmus was generally present; and sometimes a few drops of dark blood were voided

* As a grateful cordial and restorative, the ale was highly acceptable to the patients; but the spruce beer was less relished, and from its aptitude to run into the acetous fermentation, it sometimes occasioned griping in the bowels. The Lime Juice supplied by the Bengal Commissariat appeared to be slightly musty, and of impaired acidity.

per anum. Tormina, as an incidental symptom, was at times complained of, but was rarely urgent, or of long continuance. The other symptoms were lividity, enlargement, bleeding, and occasionally sloughing of the gums; pain, hardness and swelling in the calves of the legs; œdema of the feet, paleness and leucophlegmatic appearance of the countenance; general debility; appetite good. In the general plan of treatment, besides the antiscorbutics already noted, the medicines I found useful in Scorbutic Dysentery, were the Carbonate of Magnesia, or small doses of Rhubarb, to obviate the tenesmus or griping;—Opiates and anodyne Clysters. For the œdematous affections of the feet, pediluvia, and frictions with stimulating liniments were employed; and a solution of Alum, or Port Wine and Vinegar, was used as a detergent gargle for the mouth. The various astringents administered with a view to strengthen the bowels, and restrain the alvine evacuations, did not answer their indications; and I was often obliged to omit them, in consequence of their cloying the stomach and injuring the appetite.

Amongst the natives of the artillery, the disease was of a still less tractable nature than amongst the Europeans: nor is this difficult to account for. While the European sick were provided with almost every comfort from the month of October, the diet of the native sick remained unimproved till

January following, by which time the Burmese population, having become pretty numerous in the town, had established a bazar, and brought to it daily their fish, vegetables, and fruit for sale; and it was still later before these commodities became so cheap as to induce a naturally penurious people to lay out their money in the purchase.

Consistent with the view taken of the exciting causes of the disease amongst the natives, it was observed that medicine had little power to effect its removal; for though the slighter and external symptoms appeared to subside under the free employment of the Nitrous Vinegar and the solution of Nitrate of Potass in Lime Juice, I consider the recovery to be mainly attributable to the amelioration of diet, and the change from a hot and moist to a cool and dry season.

It might have been supposed that Vinegar and Lime Juice, in combination with the Nitrate of Potass, from the compound possessing diuretic as well as antiscorbutic properties, would have been peculiarly suited to the case of those in whom hydropic symptoms supervened; but I cannot say I ever saw any permanent benefit obtained from their use. At times indeed, the oppressed and laborious respiration would be relieved, and an evident detumescence take place of the anasarca swellings. This, however, was but a short re-

spite from suffering:—the strength continued progressively to decline; the dyspnæa and cuticular dropsy returned in an aggravated degree; the remedies (including the auxiliaries, Squills, Digitalis, &c.) produced no effect, and the patients died with all the symptoms of hydrothorax.

I here close my remarks on the three principal diseases which prevailed in the British army at Rangoon. Remittent and Intermittent Fevers and Cholera remain to be considered, and will form the subjects of a future paper.
